

Sustainable livelihood through scientifically optimized pond based fishery interventions using farm made fish feeds by women SHGs in some marginalized regions of Ganjam, Odisha.

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Abstract

Carp polyculture is Buzzword in modern aquaculture intervention in developing countries to enhance aquaculture production as measure for sustainable fisheries enterprise. Ganjam district of Odisha is gifted with 11580 ha. of freshwater, 4023.04 ha. of brackish water as potential for making a tragic shift from a capture based fishery to culture based fishery. Targeting enhanced production aquaculture enterprises is making a dramatic shift towards intensification. Aquaculture intensification is leading to alteration of water quality parameters such as DO, TDN, TDS and also bring eutrophication and accumulation of microbial toxins in water body resulting in fish mortality and decrease in aquaculture production and concurrent economic losses. In the current trend women SHGs are taking and prioritizing fishery enterprise to boost family income, livelihood and safeguarding food and nutrition security. Two types of aquaculture interventions carried out of which type 1 ponds almost without any feed formulation and type 2 ponds with farm made fish feeds. Farm made fish feeds with the locally available nutrients like cow dung, diverse oil cakes, rice husks though nutrient based optimized approaches increased the production by 6.5 times. Interviewing 120 members of 12 different female SHGs in six revenue blocks by the use of PRA tools using organized semi-structured questionnaire yielded necessary data. Two way ANOVA for type 1 and Type 2 intervention results implied that the production and revenue generated in two different types of aquaculture intervention ponds is statistically significant and the results showed the 'F' value between 12.131 and 246.652 statistical significance at the level of $p < 0.01$.

Key words: Sustainable livelihood. Pond based fishery. Natural fish feed, Ganjam district

1. Introduction

Aquaculture is the most emergent among food production sector involving animals in most developing countries as it boosts income generation along with provision of livelihood, employment, and food and nutrition security (Sultana et al, 2016). Farming for aquatic food

production is known to human civilization and this is done as a practice since last 2000 years but commercial aspect is realized much later in 20th century (Stickney, 2000). Aquaculture has shown a positive trend in growth since 1950s and capture fisheries has not shown any growth after 1990s. Production volume through aquaculture crossed the production of capture fisheries in 2016(FAO, 2020a). Further, in the year 2018, aquaculture stands to about 52% of the total aquatic animal food production meant for human consumption (FAO, 2020a,c). Population explosion executed greater demand on aquatic food production hence commercial aquaculture increased nearly to 124% in between 2008 to 2020(Tacon et al, 2011;Tacon and Metian,2015).

Fishery and aquaculture made a provision for recruiting about 58.5 million people directly in the primary sector in 2020 (FAO, 2022). Women are indispensable component in fishery supply and value chain. They contribute amazingly to both capture and culture fisheries but their contribution is often ignored and invisible to the society (Luomba, 2003). Women constitute 21% of workforce in primary fisheries and aquaculture sector and increasing to 50% employment in entire value chain in the sector with nearly 50% in fish processing and as full time worker and 71% as part time worker. Near about 2.1 million women involve in small scale fisheries (Harper et al, 2020). Women engagement is not only taken to be an social issue rather farther reach towards economic, labour ecological view point(Kleiber, et al,2014;Weeratunge et al.,2010). But, despite of their critical role in the sector their engagement is limited to informal, low paid, least stable and less skilled segment due gender discrimination and hence seems to the bottleneck for exploring and benefitting from the sector (FAO,2022). Women are central to the society when poverty alleviation is taken to be prioritized goal even in short, medium or long term basis (World Bank, 1986). Women are the backbone of the family, society, nation and the whole world. But, these communities are the resources which are undervalued, underprivileged and underutilized in many parts of the world. But, due to some international effort and policy decisions the scenario is improving across many countries (Nandeesh, 2001). Hence women participation in the fishery and aquaculture sector can be a gateway to sustainable livelihood in developing nations. Targeting UN's SDG 7 for conservation of natural resources and transformation towards food security, the expected rise of aquaculture may be around 15% by 2030. The primary target for it is sustainable aquatic food system with less pollution, larger biodiversity making a provision for food and nutrition security, social well being and equality (FAO, 2022).

Aquaculture basically classified as extensive (without administration of any fish feeds), semi-intensive (moderate fish feed application) and intensive (large amount of commercial feed application). Fish raised through application of commercial and farm made fish application reach adequate size and proper harvest weight faster as compared to normal extensive system making aquaculture enterprise more profitable one (Hasan et al., 2007). Aquaculture without seed input is not profitable and can only substantiate individual consumption. The major challenge in aquaculture practices is the cost of feed which constitute nearly 60% of the cost of entire fish production and the supplementary feed protein is the most expensive one among all the components of commercial fish feed (Yang et al., 2003; Erondy et al., 2006). A sizeable proportion of commercial fish feed derived from Fish Meal (FM) and Fish Oil (FO) derived from the forage fish caught from wild (Shepherd and Jackson, 2013). Further, potential exploitation of the low value trash fish or forage fish for production of FM and FO rich commercial fish feed encouraged overfishing which brought many adverse environmental consequences into action by disturbing aquatic food web, resulted in decrease in wild fish catch even from marine environment leading to decrease and sea food availability and resulted food insecurity (Naylor et al, 2009; Cao et al, 2015). Aquaculture feed producing industry is making substantial effort to reduce the use of FM and FO in commercial aquaculture feeds (Naylor et al, 2009; Tacon et al, 2011) and they are increasingly including agricultural crop products and residues as an alternative (Tacon et al, 2011).

Ganjam district of Odisha is gifted with 11580 ha. of freshwater, 4023.04 ha. of brackish water. Potential inland water resources boosted tragic shift from a capture based fishery to culture based fishery intervention contributing towards employment generation, food, nutritional and livelihood security. Women empowerment is becoming in buzz word and trend in the light of developmental perspective in developing countries like India where 2001 was declared as the women empowerment year. But, gender disparities with regard to women in aquaculture was first addressed in the FAO-NORAD supported workshop named “Women in Aquaculture” carried out in the year 1987 (Nash et al., 1987). Aquaculture industry is not so labour intensive and hence inclusion of women to considerable proportion can not only bridge the gender disparities rather provide multifarious benefit in terms of livelihood development, employment, economic upliftment. But explicit support and intensive involvement is still not achieved in many countries. At many places customary beliefs,

regulatory laws debarr the women community to go for adequate access to fishery resources and hence active participation and involvement (FAO, 2006; Porter, 2006; Okali and Holvoet, 2007).

Women SHGs members of the selected blocks of Ganjam district are having a poor or no education background and did not have sufficient technical knowledge to opt for intensive aquaculture which is highly sensitive and need constant technical monitoring in addition to huge investment. Intensive aquaculture sometimes shows over feeding which is not only the loss of expensive foods but alter the physiochemical parameter of aquatic system by reducing the dissolved oxygen, increasing the BOD and bacterial load (Craig and Helfrich, 2002). As they have poor financial infrastructure and credit facilities they frequently use locally available fish feeds available to them in local areas. Our study targeted to know about semi intensive mode of for aquaculture with the use of locally available farm made fish feed components and the benefits to the livelihood of local women SHGs for sustainable production.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Research sites and aquaculture interventions

Ganjam is among the top in fisheries and aquaculture production among 30 districts of Odisha. Six different blocks of the Ganjam district including Aska, Bellguntha, Bhanjanagar, Polasara, Rangeilunda and Surada were included for the study of aquaculture intervention in terms of feed use and fish production. Two fish ponds in the village areas of each site were selected for the study and the study was conducted from June 2022 to May 2023. In total, twelve moderate sized ponds of about one acre each were selected as fish culture ponds for investigation of fish production under different pond management condition. Type 1 pond taken without any farm feed application and only small amount of rice bran with cow dung. Type 2 pond managed with scientifically formulated farm made components with locally available components like oil cakes, rice bran and wheat bran.

2.2 Methods of data collection

Twelve women SHGs of six revenue blocks with 120 members those are directly or indirectly involved in fishery enterprise were interviewed with pre-structured questionnaire using PRA tools This is responsible for generating a comprehensive data in the present study. The data collected from twelve different ponds (Six without the use of fish feeds and six with use of farm made fish feeds).

2.3 Statistical analysis

Data collected from the twelve aquaculture ponds i.e. six involving the use of cow dung and rice bran and six others with additional use of locally available farm made fish feeds were separately arranged in excel sheets. Two separate data were compared by using the ANOVA test to know the significance of difference between two types of aquaculture interventions if any. The results for investments, production and cost benefit calculation are made for finding statistical significance if any.

3. Results and discussion

The interview of the female SHGs members resulted in drawing a conclusion that the female stake holders belonging to different areas were involved in aquaculture activities. They are involved in all phases of aquaculture including pond preparation, feeding, fish capture, selling and post harvesting processing of fish(Fig.1,2,3 and 4).

Fig.1. Female stake holders during questionnaire

Fig.2. Women SHG members applying fish feeds

Fig.3. SHG members involved in fish production

Fig.4. SHGs members involved in fish sales

Two type of aquaculture In the type 1 ponds the investment with respect to feed as was very low i.e. 576 per acre(Kg@INR 6 and total of 96 Kg). This investment incurred due to application of rice bran which is homely ,made or locally avialble with very low cost The cowdung applied is locally available with free of cost. In type 2 pond farm made fish used with locally available fish feeds including rice bran,wheat bran and othe oil cakes.In addition proper pond management was performed by use of lime and probiotics incurred additional costs .Cost of fingerling same in both type of pond @ INR 3.5 per fingerling. Total investment in type 1 and 2 pond are INR 5826 and INR 15802 respectively.

We have monitored the pond management carried out be respective fish farmer. In type 1 pond as the fish feed is not used and fish growth solely influenced by natural productivity of the pond. The survival rate and hence production was found to be low. Survival rate of Rohu, *Mrigal* and *Catla* was respectively 39%, 37% and 36% respectively. Average weight of Rohu, *Mrigal* and *Catla* was found to be 430 gm, 420 gm and 460 gm respectively. In type 2 pond The average survival rate observed in all these locations was found to be 90% for Rohu, 87% for *Mrigal* and 86% for *Catla* in the intervention with the supply of farm made fish feeds with locally available ingredients such as rice bran, mustard oil cake, wheat bran, coconut oil cake, Til oil cake. Proper management with the use of farm made fish feeds reflected a large amount of fish production as compared to the fish production in pond without any artificial fish feed supply. Some large sized fishes were harvested in the month of March and final harvest was made in the month of May.. With the introduction of same numbers of fingerlings the mean production is found to be less in type 1 intervention as compared to the type 2 intervention. The revenue generated in the type 1 intervention is INR 239359 with a net profit of INR 2, 23,557. In type 1 pond the mean revenue generated is 40,204 with a net profit of INR 34,378.98. The difference in investments in both types of intervention is INR 9976. But, the production difference is very high of about 1165.28 Kg with a net profit difference of about INR 1, 89,178. Mean of production of in type 1 ponds calculated to be 47.361 with calculated F – value of 246.652 with a statistical level of significance at $p < 0.01$ (Table 1). The mean of order of production found to be Rohu>*Catla*>*mirgal*(Table 1, Fig.5) with a C.D. Value 0.571 and SE(m) if 0.179.

Table1. Analysis of Variance for fish production in six sampling ponds (each one acre pond area) without use of any fish feeds and revenue generated in INR

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	5	36.646			
Treatment	2	94.862	47.431	246.652	0.00000
Error	10	1.923	0.192		
Total	17	133.431			

	Mean	S.E.
1- Rohu	83.428 ^a	0.608
2- Catla	80.308 ^b	0.640
3- Mrigal	77.817 ^c	0.712
C.D.	0.571	
SE(m)	0.179	
SE(d)	0.253	
C.V.	0.545	

Fig.5 Mean fish production without feed

The revenue generated in type 1 intervention was found to be 15,244.066 with calculated 'F' value of 198.786 with $p < 0.01$. With mean of revenue generated out of three species concerned followed Rohu > Mrigal > Catla having a C.D. value of 160.882 and SE(m) found to be 50.405.

Table.2 Analysis of Variance for revenue generation in INR in six sampling ponds (each one acre pond area) without use of any fish feeds.

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	5	812,599.808			
Treatment	2	6,060,604.926	3,030,302.463	198.786	0.00000
Error	10	152,440.661	15,244.066		
Total	17	7,025,645.394			

	Mean	S.E.
1- Rohu	14,182.820 ^a	103.304
2- Catla	12,793.330 ^c	82.748
3- Mrigal	13,228.830 ^b	121.047
C.D.	160.882	
SE(m)	50.405	
SE(d)	71.284	
C.V.	0.921	

Further, when the fish production observed in type 2 ponds the mean calculated to be 2,583.722 with calculated value of 'F' is found to be 18.697 which is statistically significant at $p < 0.01$ (Table 3). The mean of production of three different ponds followed the order Rohu > Catla > Mrigal (Table 3 and Fig.6) with C.D. value of 15.318 and SE(m) of 4.799.

Table3. Fish production in six sampling ponds (each one-acre pond area) with the use of farm made fish feeds using locally available ingredients and revenue generated in INR

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	5	1,459.611			
Treatment	2	5,167.444	2,583.722	18.697	0.00042
Error	10	1,381.889	138.189		
Total	17	8,008.944			

	Mean	S.E.
1- Rohu	489.833 ^a	4.643
2- Catla	468.667 ^b	7.018
3- Mrigal	448.333 ^c	4.890
C.D.	15.318	
SE(m)	4.799	
SE(d)	6.787	
C.V.	2.507	

Fig.6.Fish production with farm made feeds

Fig.7 Revenue generation in INR

When analysis of variation of revenue generation in two types of pond with two different types of feeding condition is compared it showed that calculated value ‘F’ was 40.849 at a statistical level of significance $p < 0.01$ (Table 4). The mean of the difference is statistically significant and the order of significance in revenue generation followed Rohu>Mrigal>Catla (Table 4 and Fig.7) and C.D. value and SE(m) are respectively 3,281.833 and 1,028.213.

Table 4. Analysis of Variance revenue generation: A comparison between two different types of interventions with different feed treatments.

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	5	74,270,294.444			
Treatment	2	518,232,411.111	259,116,205.556	40.849	0.00002
Error	10	63,433,322.222	6,343,332.222		
Total	17	655,936,027.778			

	Mean	S.E.
1- Rohu	87,370.000 ^a	1,380.210
2- Catla	75,771.660 ^b	1,412.157
3- Mrigal	76,216.660 ^b	831.331
C.D.	3,281.833	
SE(m)	1,028.213	
SE(d)	1,454.113	
C.V.	3.157	

When analysis of variance is compared between mode of operation and type of fish in 12 different ponds then calculated 'F' between two was found to be 12.131 at level of significance $p < 0.01$ (Table 5 and Table 6).

Table 5. Analysis of Variance of fish production in 12 sampling ponds (each one acre pond area) in both mode of operation and cost benefit calculation

Source of Variation	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-Calculated	Significance
Replication	5	889.127			
Factor A-Mode of operation	1	1,357,877.318	1,357,877.318	17,050.687	0.00000
Factor B-Fish Type	2	3,330.202	1,665.101	20.908	0.00000
Interaction A X B	2	1,932.105	966.053	12.131	0.00021
Error	25	1,990.942	79.638		
Total	35	1,366,019.694			

Table 6. Analysis of Variance of fish production Two Way Mean Table

	B1	B2	B3	Mean A
A1	83.428	80.308	77.817	80.518
A2	489.833	468.667	448.333	468.945
Mean B	286.631	274.488	263.075	

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(A)	6.162	2.975	2.103
Factor(B)	7.546	3.643	2.576
Factor(A X B)	10.672	5.152	3.643

Two way mean table showed that mean of the production showed a greater variation as 80.518 and 468.945 with mean of three different fish species as 286. 631(for Rohu), 274.488 (for Catla) and 263.075 (for Mrigal). C.D values for both the types of pond intervention and profit out of them was found to be 10.672 and SE (m) is 3.643 which is statistically more significant.

When production of fish in two types of intervention is studied then

4. Conclusion

It has been observed that women of the rural area of the region show emergence in the aquaculture enterprises through their SHGs network and involved in almost all fishery activities. Adoption of fishery activities leading to increase in women empowerment index in terms in increase in revenue generation, family income. The rural SHGs sometimes losing technical expertise, financial burdens due to proper credit facilities and women friendly fishery enterprise infrastructure and hence is the actual constraints for women SHGs fish farmers. Optimization of technology with adequate management including balanced fish feed use, overall pond management women friendly policy formulations for women SHGs members can be appropriately address their problems and help them for development of sustainable fishery enterprises as a step forward towards women empowerment.

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6. References

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